

Some Guanyl Hydroxyaryl Sulphides and Disulphides (Hydrobromides)

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The interaction of various simple phenols and their acetates with bis-formamidine disulphide dihydrobromide has been shown to afford related hydroxyaryl guanyl sulphides and disulphide salts. The structure of some of these products have been confirmed by synthesis. Mechanism of the reaction has been discussed.

When bis-formamidine disulphide dihydrobromide is allowed to react with certain phenols and phenolic esters, mostly acetates, two types of products, viz., the corresponding hydroxyaryl guanyl disulphide hydrobromides (I) and hydroxyaryl guanyl sulphide hydrobromides (II) are obtained, depending on the nature of the substituents on the phenolic nucleus and the reaction conditions:

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| (a) Ar = 4-hydroxyphenyl-
(b) Ar = 2-chloro-4-hydroxyphenyl-
(c) Ar = 2-bromo-4-hydroxyphenyl- | (a) Ar = 4-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl-
(b) Ar = 2, 4-dihydroxyphenyl
(c) Ar = 2-hydroxynaphthyl- |
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The sulphides (II) can be looked upon as S-hydroxyphenyl isothiuronium salts, some of which have been prepared earlier by the action of thiocarbamides with quinones^{1,2,3}, a procedure, evidently, limited to quinones only. Thus:

The disulphides of type (I) do not appear to have been prepared before and are unsymmetrical disulphides containing a thioformamidine system and a thiophenol moiety.

1. Snell and Weinsberger, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 450.
2. Burton and David, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 2193.
3. Wenzlik, *Angew. Chem.*, 1960, 72, 581.

which are hydrobromides, appear from their composition to contain a thioformamidine moiety joined to the phenolic nucleus. These products are found unreactive towards aqueous potassium iodide and hydrogen sulphide. On treatment with cold dilute ammonia, unlike the disulphides (Ia-c), related free bases can be obtained. Strong alkali solution, however, decomposes them into the corresponding hydroxythiophenols, benzoyl derivatives of which are isolated from the alkali solutions on treatment with benzoyl chloride.

The product from *o*-cresol and its acetate has been assigned structure (IIa), confirmed by its synthesis from 4-hydroxy-3-methylthiophenol,^{10,11} and formamidine hydrochloride:

As expected it does not afford a benzothioxolone derivative (cf. ref.²) which would be formed if the thioamidine and hydroxy groups were *ortho* with respect to each other.

The product, $\text{C}_7\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$, from resorcinol or its diacetate on reaction with acetic acid and sodium acetate forms the benzothioxolone, identical with a product obtained by the direct thiocyanation of resorcinol.¹² There has been some controversy about the structure of this product. Of the two probable structures, viz., 1'-hydroxy-4:5-benzothioxol-2-one¹³ and 3'-hydroxy-4:5-benzothioxol-2-one,¹⁴ from the general pattern of substitution reactions of resorcinol, we prefer the latter for our product. The dibenzoyl derivative obtained from (IIb) and benzothioxolone¹⁵ have also been found identical.

The product, $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{OS}$, HBr from β -naphthyl acetate, affords a thioxolone identical with the one formed from β -naphthol by direct thiocyanation¹⁴ and has been assigned structure (IIc). The benzoyl derivatives of the related thiols obtained by alkaline benzoylation of the product and the thioxolone are also found identical.

Although *oresol* and phenol do not differ very much in their reactivity, we are unable to obtain the expected disulphides in the case of *cresol* and monosulphide in the case of phenol. This same is true with other phenolic esters. This, perhaps, needs to be investigated further.

The yields of disulphides (Ia-c) are generally quite low, the highest in the case of phenyl acetate, phenol and anisole are 34.8%, 16.0% and 28.8% respectively. With *m*-chlorophenol and *m*-bromophenol the yields of the respective products are 57.1 and 30.5%. As a rule, esters afford better yields of the products than the free phenols. Addition of small quantities of elemental sulphur and hydrobromic acid has a definite favourable influence on the yields of the disulphide salts.

10. Leuskerb, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1890, 41, 170.

11. Kresmer, "Org. Syn. Coll.," Vol. 1, p. 511.

12. Yoshiyuki Urushibara and Gen. Koga, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1956, 29, 419.

13. Fanlitschko & Benger, *Monatsh.*, 1950, 81, 393.

14. Hisao Tsukamoto *et al.*, *J. Pharm. Soc., Japan*, 1953, 73, 1093.

The yields of monosulphide salts (IIa-c) are generally much higher; *o*-cresol acetate, resorcinol diacetate and β -naphthyl acetate under most favourable conditions afford 24, 64 and 75% yields of the expected sulphide salts. A shorter duration of heating time ($1\frac{1}{2}$ to 2 hrs.) is necessary. Addition of elemental sulphur and hydrobromic acid to the reaction mixture does not have any favourable influence on the yields of these products. The following tentative mechanism is suggested for the reactions.

Bis-formamidine disulphide first dissociates into sulphide and sulphenyl ions. The sulphenium ion then reacts with the phenols and its derivatives by a process of electrophilic substitution giving the products (II).

CHART I

Where $\text{R} = \text{OH}$ or Methyl

In case of the products (I), the phenols or derivatives are most probably first sulphurated by the elemental sulphur¹⁵⁻¹⁶ which is available from the decomposition of bis-formamidine disulphide salts or has been added as such to the reaction mixture. The thiophenols then react with the sulphenium ion furnishing the sulphides (I).

Since the bis-formamidine disulphide or the disulphides (Ia-c) formed in the above process can be stabilised by salt formation only, the favourable role of the added acid in this reaction is obvious. The final product, the disulphide (Ia-c), is preceded by another reaction, viz., sulphurisation of phenols which is known to be a slow process and as the product itself is unstable, its comparatively low yields are understandable. The differential behaviour of very similar phenols leading to two entirely different products (I & II) is.

15. Hotelling *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1959, 24, 1598.

16. Lefevre and Desgrosch, *Compt. rend.*, 1884, 188, 1791.

CHART II

where $R = \text{H}, \text{Cl}$ or Br and $R' = \text{H}, \text{CH}_3$ or OAc

however, very difficult to understand. The slightly increased reactivity of cresol, resorcinol, and naphthol might be a probable cause.

EXPERIMENTAL

Guanyl-4-hydroxyphenyl Disulphide Hydrobromide (Ia).—Bis-formamidine disulphide dihydrobromide (6.5 g.) and phenyl acetate (3 ml), were heated at 120° for 8 hr. On cooling the reaction mixture was washed successively with acetone, carbon disulphide and cold water when a colorless crystalline solid was obtained (1.0 g.) (17.4%); on crystallisation from dil. aq. HBr it had m.p. 204° (decomp.) (Found: C, 30.22; H, 3.13; N, 9.88; S, 23.05. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{OS}_2$, HBr requires: C, 29.89; H, 3.20; N, 9.96; S, 22.79%).

Addition of sulphur (0.5 g.) to the above reaction mixture increased the yield to 34.8%. With addition of hydrobromic acid (1 ml.) and heating for 2 hrs., the yield was 26.8%. Phenyl benzoate and anisole reacted in the presence of hydrobromic acid, when heated for 2 and 3 hrs., with respective yields of 9.0% and 13.6%. Phenol (3 ml.) on similar heating for 2 hrs., in presence of sulphur (0.5 g.) and hydrobromic acid (1 ml.) afforded 0.9 g. of the product corresponding to a yield of 16%, whereas under the same condition phenyl acetate afforded 1.5 g. of the product (27%).

The product on boiling with dilute sulphuric acid afforded a sparingly soluble sulphate, m.p. 184° (decomp.) (Found: C, 34.69; H, 3.83; N, 11.32; S, 31.76 and SO_4 , 19.4. $(\text{C}_7\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{OS}_2)_2$, H_2SO_4 requires: C, 33.73; H, 3.61; N, 11.04; S, 32.2 and SO_4 , 19.27%). The hydrobromide on crystallisation from aq. hydrochloric acid furnished the hydrochloride. (m.p. 189° decomp.) (Found: N, 11.47. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{OS}_2\cdot\text{HCl}$ requires: N, 11.83%). It also afforded a picrate, m.p. 173° . Though stable towards dilute acids, Ia was found unsta-

ble in an alkaline medium affording yellow solution which on benzoylation formed two benzoyl derivatives: an alkali insoluble one and another alkali soluble precipitated on acidification. The latter crystallised from ethanol, and had m.p. 172° (Found: N, 15.26. Calc. for $C_9H_9N_3OS$: N, 15.55%). It was proved to be identical with N-benzoyl thiocarbamide (mixed m.p.) The alkali insoluble benzoyl derivative crystallised from ethanol-benzene, and had m.p. 165° (Found: S, 9.17. Calc. for $C_{10}H_9O_2S$: S, 9.58%). It was found identical (mixed m.p.) with the dibenzoyl derivative⁷ of thiohydroquinone (reported m.p. 160-1°). On reaction with dilute aq. ammonia it (Ia) decomposed; on evaporating the solution, thiocarbamide, m.p. 178° and thiohydroquinone (identified through its dibenzoate) were obtained.

Syntheses: (i) Bis-formamidine disulphide dihydrobromide (3.1g) and thiohydroquinone⁶ (1.2g) were mixed into a paste and allowed to stand overnight. The reaction mixture on being washed with acetone followed by water, afforded a solid (1.3g) which crystallised from dil. HBr-acid, and had m.p. 204° (decomp.) (Found: C, 30.15; H, 3.26; N, 0.69; S, 22.52. Calc. for $C_7H_9N_3OS_2$, HBr: C, 29.85; H, 3.20; N, 0.98; S, 22.79%). No depression in m.p. was observed on mixing the product, its picrate and sulphate, respectively, with the corresponding salts described above.

(ii) Thiocarbamide hydrochloride (1.2g) and bis-*p*-hydroxyphenyl disulphide⁷ (2.5g) were mixed intimately and left overnight. The reaction mixture on being washed with water yielded a hydrochloride (0.2g), m.p. 189° (decomp.), found identical in all respects with the hydrochloride described above. However, when bis-formamidine disulphide dihydrobromide and *p*-hydroxy diphenyl disulphide were mixed together no exchange occurred.

Guanyl-2-chloro-4-hydroxyphenyl Disulphide Hydrobromide (Ib): Bis-formamidine disulphide dihydrobromide (6.3g), *m*-chlorophenol (3 ml), sulphur (0.5g) and hydrobromic acid (1 ml), were mixed and heated at 120° for 2 hrs. The reaction mixture was worked up as in the case of Ia, and afforded a hydrobromide 3.7g (57.1%) which crystallised from dilute hydrobromic acid and had m.p. 221° (decomp.) (Found: C, 27.16; H, 2.90; N, 8.76; S, 19.87. Reqd. for $C_7H_7ClN_3OS_2$, HBr: C, 26.62; H, 2.59; N, 8.87; S, 20.28%). The same product was obtained in lesser yield when no free sulphur was added. The product with boiling dil. sulphuric acid afforded a sulphate, m.p. 178° [Found: SO_4 , 16.58. Calc. for $(C_7H_7ClN_3OS_2)_2 \cdot H_2SO_4$: 16.9%]. It also gave a picrate, m.p. 166°. Like Ia, it was stable to acids but decomposed on treatment with alkalis. With sodium hydroxide it afforded a yellow solution which on benzoylation, gave alkali soluble N-benzoyl thiocarbamide, m.p. 172° and another alkali insoluble dibenzoate, m.p. 132° (Found: S, 8.35. Reqd. for $C_{10}H_9ClO_2S$, S, 8.69%), identified as the dibenzoate of 2-chloro-4-hydroxythiophenol.

Synthesis: Bis-formamidine disulphide dihydrobromide (3.1g) and 2-chloro-4-hydroxy thiophenol were mixed and left to stand for 4 days. The reaction mixture on being washed with acetone and water afforded a hydrobromide (2g) (crystallised from dil. hydrobromic acid), m.p. 221° (decomp.) (Found: C, 26.53; H, 2.30. Calc. for $C_6H_7ClN_3OS_2$, HBr: C, 26.62; H, 2.59%). The hydrobromide and also the sulphate, m.p. 178° gave no depression in m.p. when mixed with the respective compounds described above.

Guanyl-2-bromo-4-hydroxyphenyl disulphide Hydrobromide (Ic): Bis-formamidine disulphide dihydrobromide (6.3g) and *m*-bromophenol (3 ml), were heated without any solvent at 120° for 2 hrs. The reaction mixture on cooling and being washed with acetone and water afforded a solid, 2.3g (30.5%), which on two crystallisations from dilute hydrochloric acid

had m.p. 194° (decomp.) (Found: N, 8.59; S, 20.23. Reqd. for $C_7H_7BrN_4OS_2$, HCl: N, 8.87; S, 20.28%).

Guanyl-4-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl Sulphide Hydrobromide (IIa): Bis-formamidino disulphide dihydrobromide (6.3 g), *o*-cresyl acetate (3 ml.) and hydrobromic acid (1 ml.) were heated at 120° for 2½ hrs. The reaction mixture on cooling and being washed with acetone and water afforded a solid, 1.3 g (24.0%), m.p. 271° (decomp.); crystallised from dil. HBr, (Found: C, 36.81; H, 4.76; Br, 30.74; N, 10.48; S, 11.87. Reqd. for $C_8H_{10}N_4OS$, HBr: C, 30.50; H, 4.18; Br, 30.41; N, 10.04; S, 12.16%). On boiling with conc. hydrochloric acid, the hydrochloride, m.p. 254° (decomp.) was obtained. It also gave a picrate, m.p. 217°. Unlike the disulphides (Ia-c) it did not liberate iodine from aq. KI nor did it have any action on aq. H_2S . Ethanolic ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide cleaved it into thiocarbamide and 4-hydroxy-3-methyl thiophenol, identified through its dibenzoyl derivative, m.p. 103° (Found: C, 72.31; H, 4.84; S, 9.65. Reqd. for $C_{11}H_{16}O_2S$: C, 72.41; H, 4.59; S, 9.19%). An authentic specimen was prepared from *p*-amino-*o*-cresol¹⁷ by Louckart's method.

Synthesis: Formamidino hydrochloride (about 1 g.) obtained by desulphurisation of thiocarbamide with yellow lead oxide in an acetone medium followed by the action of hydrogen chloride and 4-hydroxy-3-methyl thiophenol. (1.5 g), were warmed on a water bath for 3 hrs.¹⁷ On cooling and washing the reaction mixture with acetone followed by water, a hydrochloride (0.5 g) was obtained which was crystallised from dilute hydrochloric acid and had m.p. 254° (decomp.) (Found: N, 13.06. Calc. for $C_8H_{10}N_4OS$, HCl; N, 13.27%). It showed no depression in m.p. when mixed with the hydrochloride obtained from IIa.

Guanyl-2,4-dihydroxyphenyl sulphide hydrobromide (IIb): Bis-formamidino disulphide dihydrobromide (6.3 g) and resorcinol diacetate (3 g.) were heated at 120° for two hrs. The reaction mixture was worked up as in preceding experiments and afforded a hydrobromide, m.p. 200° (3.4 g; 64.1%) which on two crystallisations from dilute hydrochloric acid yielded the related hydrochloride m.p. 185° (decomp.) (Found: C, 37.14; H, 4.04; N, 12.52; S, 14.30. Reqd. for $C_7H_9N_4O_2S$, HCl: C, 38.09; H, 4.08; N, 12.69; S, 14.51%). The hydrobromide on basification afforded the free base, m.p. 155° (Found: N, 15.03; S, 16.92. Reqd. for $C_7H_9N_4O_2S$: N, 15.21; S, 17.39%). It also furnished a picrate, m.p. 195°. On benzylation it afforded the tri-benzoate of 2,4-dihydroxy thiophenol which crystallised from alcohol-benzene, and had m.p. 122° (Found: S, 7.32. Reqd. for $C_{17}H_{16}O_3S$: S, 7.0%). On treatment with ethanolic ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide the hydrobromide afforded thiocarbamide and a greenish semisolid which on standing hardened; this was probably bis-2,4-dihydroxyphenyl disulphide, m.p. 168-70°; on benzylation it gave a tetrabenzoate, m.p. 107° (Found: S, 8.96. Reqd. for $C_{16}H_{16}O_4S_2$: S, 9.16%).

3-hydroxy-4:5-benzothiazol-2-one: The hydrobromide (IIb) (3 g.) was refluxed with a mixture of glacial acetic acid (15 ml.), sodium acetate (1 g.) and water (4 ml.) for 2 hrs. The reaction mixture on cooling and dilution afforded a solid (1.8 g) which crystallised from aq. ethanol, and had m.p. 160° (Found: S, 18.78. Calc. for $C_7H_4O_3S$: S, 19.04%). It gave no depression in m.p. when mixed with an authentic specimen (m.p. 159°) prepared by direct thiocyanation of resorcinol¹⁸. On treatment with alkaline benzoyl chloride it hydrolysed and afforded a tribenzoate, m.p. 122°, found identical with the tribenzoyl derivative obtained from thiophenol formed by the decomposition of IIb.

17. Loev and Kormanly, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, 27, 3365.

Guanyl-2-hydroxynaphthyl Sulphide Hydrobromide (IIc): Bis-formamidine disulphide dihydrobromide (0.3 g.) and β -naphthyl acetate (4.0 g.) were heated at 110° for 1½ hrs. and worked up as in other similar experiments. The product (4.7 g., 75%) crystallised from ethanolic hydrobromic acid and had m.p. 220° (decomp.) (Found: C, 45.37; H, 3.73; N, 9.00; S, 10.29. Reqd. for $C_{11}H_{10}N_2OS$, HBr: C, 44.14; H 3.67; N, 9.36; S, 10.70%). On basification with cold dil. aq. ammonia the related base was obtained m.p. 122-3° (Found: N, 12.59; S, 14.35. Reqd. for $C_{11}H_{10}N_2OS$: N, 12.84; S, 14.67%). On treatment with ethanolic ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide and evaporation of the solvent, the hydrobromide furnished thiocarbamide and a yellow solid identified as bis-(2-hydroxynaphthyl) disulphide crystallised from ethanol with m.p. 170° (reported¹⁴ m.p. 164°). On benzylation the hydrobromide afforded a dibenzoate, crystallised from ethanol-benzene with m.p. 193° (Found: S, 8.02. Reqd. for $C_{24}H_{18}O_2S$: S, 8.33%).

4 : 5-*Naphthothiazol-2-one*: The hydrobromide (IIc) (3 g.), glacial acetic acid (15 ml.), sodium acetate (1 g.) and water (4 ml.) were refluxed for 2 hrs. On cooling the reaction mixture deposited a yellow fluffy solid (2.1 g.), crystallised from methanol, m.p. 107° (Found: C, 65.12; H 2.63 S, 15.43. Reqd. for $C_{11}H_8O_2S$: C, 65.34; H, 2.97; S, 15.84%). This was found to be identical with the sample prepared by thiocyanation of β -naphthol.¹⁴ (mixed m.p.). It afforded a benzoyl derivative, m.p. 193°, identical with the benzoyl-derivative from the hydrobromide (IIc).

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